

Towards Patient-Driven Phenotyping and Similarity for Precision Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Clinical phenotyping techniques provide clinicians and clinical researchers with important insight into the treatment of rare and complex diseases for a population of patients. Many, traditional methods require multiple iterations of refinement with a domain expert, lack generalizability and interoperability, and often have limited reproducibility. Compared to traditional phenotyping approaches, patient similarity-based techniques aim to derive personalized patient risk models. Although relatively new, these methods have already been shown to be more accurate, even when applied to sparse data or poorly characterized diseases/phenotypes. Here, we present preliminary results from an initial evaluation of a novel data-driven method for calculating patient similarity.

Background/Objective

Clinical phenotyping, or the classification of patients with and without a disease, is a technique designed to provide clinicians with important insight into the development, progression, and outcome of complex diseases for a population of patients. While there is a large body of research supporting the successful implementation of existing methods, these approaches often require multiple iterations of refinement, lack generalizability and interoperability, and have limited reproducibility.¹⁻³ Compared to traditional phenotyping approaches, patient similarity-based techniques aim to derive personalized risk models for each patient. When compared to other methods leveraging global and local models, patient similarity-based approaches have shown to be more accurate,⁴ even when applied to sparse data or poorly characterized diseases/phenotypes.⁵ While these approaches are scalable and accurate, they still suffer from poor handling of missing data, reliance on domain expertise, and a lack of robust internal and external validation. The current project aimed to address some of the limitations of traditional phenotyping and existing patient similarity-based methods by developing a novel, data-driven algorithm for patient-level phenotyping and similarity. This podium abstract summarizes the preliminary results from an initial proof-of-concept evaluation.

Methods

The composite patient similarity algorithm was designed specifically for use with the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model (CDM). By developing our method specifically for this CDM, we can access pre-normalized data that has been standardized to a specific set of clinical terminologies. We developed the composite patient similarity algorithm by leveraging existing pairwise⁶ and groupwise⁷ semantic similarity measures. Pairwise similarity scores were calculated for demographic attributes, accounting for binary (e.g., gender), categorical (e.g., race), and continuous (e.g., age) variables. Additional pairwise and groupwise similarity scores were calculated for clinical attributes by incorporating hierarchical relations from standard clinical terminologies (e.g., LOINC⁸, RxNorm⁹, and SNOMED CT¹⁰,). The final similarity score between two patients was calculated as a weighted average of the individual demographic and clinical similarities. While attribute weights can be chosen by the user, the current analysis did not apply any differential weighting.

A proof-of-concept evaluation of the composite patient similarity algorithm was performed using de-identified Children's Hospital of Colorado (CHCO) data stored in the University of Colorado Denver's

Anschutz Medical Campus Health Data Compass warehouse. CHCO data conforms to the structure defined by the Pediatric Learning Health System (PEDSnet) OMOP CDM, which is an adaptation of the OMOP CDM version 5.0.^{11,12} The condition occurrence, drug exposure, measurement, observation, and procedures tables were considered for analysis. Using these data, we retrieved demographic and clinical data and constructed two groups of 10 patients having the highest counts of the diagnoses cystic fibrosis (CF) identified by ICD-9-CM 277.0 and Huntington's Chorea (HC) identified by ICD-9-CM 333.4. Once the composite patient similarity scores were calculated, agglomerative hierarchical clustering with complete linkage and Euclidean distance was used to generate clusters of similar patients. Clustering results were then interpreted by visualization using dendrograms and heat maps. Use of the data for the analyses described in this project was approved by the Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board (protocol # 15-0445).

Results

Patients were predominately white (90%) and female (60%) with a median age of 19. On average, CF patients were older (22.1 vs. 17.4) and had a greater average number of conditions (849.6 vs. 256.7), measurements (3120.3 vs. 1528.7), medications (2495.9 vs. 99.7), observations (676.0 vs. 276.7), and procedures (836.6 vs. 183.4) than HC patients. Hierarchical clustering, using all clinical variables and patient age, resulted in four clusters of patients. The first (n=3) and second (n=2) clusters contained HC patients differing primarily by age. The third cluster (n=9) contained CF patients. The final cluster (n=6) contained 5 HC patients and 1 CF patient. Closer examination revealed that HC patients in this cluster had a high frequency of lung-related diagnoses and that the CF patient had very few CF-related diagnoses compared to the other CF patients.

Discussion

We are currently developing a novel data-driven method to measure patient similarity and provided an initial proof-of-concept using two small groups of pediatric patients. Clustering results demonstrated the algorithm's ability to successfully identify meaningful groups and sub-groups of similar patients. Additional work is needed including: conducting a more comprehensive and robust evaluation; running the algorithm on larger patient groups; and accounting for or incorporating specific changes in clinical variables over time, learning variable weights.

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